

Nongovernmental Organizations and Peacebuilding in the Northeastern Nigeria: Exploring the Problems

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Abstract

Boko Haram insurgency and other related crimes like banditry and kidnapping have left dire human and economic consequences on the Northeast region. The government and NGOs have been carrying out various peacebuilding interventions that have been marred by myriads of problems. This paper explored these problems through interviews, a structured questionnaire, and extant literature. The study was set in Borno and Adamawa states, and 20 NGOs staff were interviewed while 200 questionnaires were distributed among a purposive sample population of NGOs staff, NEMA officials and security agents. The results provide a concise exposition into the broad-based and community-based problems of peacebuilding, including lack of government cooperation and commitment, continued insecurity and displacement, inadequate regional cooperation, ungoverned spaces, and lack of adequate funding among others. To this end, based on the MTD model, the study recommends a multistakeholder engagement in order to surmount these problems and build the peace edifice in Nigeria

Keywords: Boko Haram, conflict, Nigeria, northeast, peacebuilding, problems

Introduction

The question of peacebuilding has become very pertinent in contemporary international system. This is not far-fetched from the fact that, almost every sovereign state is experiencing one conflict or the other. All over the world today, as in classical civilisations, conflicts, violence, and outright wars have been part of mankind. The general explanation to this phenomenology of violence is that conflict

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is inevitable (Abeeb, 2020) because of the constant struggles over scarce power, status and resources. This disposition is based on the natural phenomenon that, as long as human beings relate with one another, there is bound to be disagreements. It is these disagreements that sometimes escalate to violent conflicts and even wars if not properly managed. Conflict therefore, is inevitable, natural, and neutral. However, violent conflict is not inevitable. This means that conflict can be managed or prevented from erupting into violence.

Various conflicts in Nigeria have taken violent dimensions since independence. The first military intervention in 1966 heralded an era of instability, human rights violations, and killings throughout the military regimes from 1966-1999 with two brief intermittent civilian regimes. The civil war of 1967-1970 is a sad example of how the country has been a fertile ground for violent conflicts (Achebe, 2013). The struggle for democracy became a reality in 1999, but conflicts did not stop. They only assumed different dimensions with additional new actors. Ethnic contestations, electoral violence, religious violence, communal violence, etc., became part and parcel of our national life. Kidnapping of expatriates and oil theft by militants in the Niger-Delta and various movements for self-determination, particularly the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) in the Southeast region of the country have all threatened the corporate existence of the Nigerian state.

Bringing the discussion specifically to the Northeast, it is not out of place to aver that, this region represents the epicenter of instability in the country since 2009. This is mainly attributed to the emergence of Boko Haram terrorist group. The activities of this terrorist group have led to so many deaths, displacements, destructions and a dire humanitarian crisis in the region (Nnam et al., 2020). Other security challenges in the region include but not limited to kidnapping for ransom, farmer-herder conflict, ethnic/religious contestations, election related violence, political unrest, banditry, and youth restiveness. The conflict situation in the Northeast has become protracted because of the high level of

structural violence in the region. It houses some of the poorest states in the country, with high mortality rate, unemployment, multidimensional poverty, disease, illiteracy, and general underdevelopment ((Akoji & Abaji 2025)). There was, and there is still need therefore, for state and non-state actors to engage in peacebuilding activities toward conflict management and conflict resolution. The question for the cost of rebuilding the Northeast therefore became pertinent and vocal among donor governments and NGOs. To answer this question, the federal government, with the World Bank, brought out a thorough report in 2016 on the assessment of the peacebuilding needs in the six states of region as at 2015. Table 1 shows the figures thus:

Table 1: An overview of recovery and peace-building needs by components (\$ million)

Components	Adama-wa	Borno	Yobe	Gombe	Taraba	Bauchi	Fed/Reg.	Total
Peacebuilding and social cohesion	27.5	37.8	22.5	13.6	19.4	23.9	5.7	150.5
Infrastructure and social services	594.9	3933.3	668.3	129.1	144.9	202.9	94.7	6040.1
Economic recovery	37.6	68.8	30.7	22.3	27.7	41.4	24.5	473.5
Total	660	4040	721.5	164.9	192	268.2	345.4	6664.1

Source: FGN Northeast, Nigeria Recovery and Peace-Building Assessment; Synthesis Report 2015

From Table 1, it is evident that infrastructure and social services were the most needed component of the peacebuilding efforts in the Northeast with \$5768 million, followed by economic recovery with a total of \$474 million. Last but certainly not the least was peacebuilding and social cohesion with \$152 million. This is not an indication that the last component is not equally important as the others, but it shows how expedient infrastructures/social services and economic recovery were for IDPs and communities affected

by the insurgency. It can also be seen that Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe were the states with highest needs. This is obviously based the fact that they were the most hit by the insurgency.

There have been various peacebuilding interventions in the region aimed at achieving durable peace and preventing violent extremism (PVE). On one hand, there is the kinetic approach to peacebuilding in the Northeast. On the other hand, there is the non-kinetic approach. On the first approach, the federal and state governments have been physically engaging Boko Haram through the Nigerian military and the Multinational Joint Task Force (MJTF) that involves neighboring states in the Lake Chad Basin. This force has recorded a lot of successes in the counter-insurgency efforts, especially with the inclusion of the Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF) (Ashindorbe et al. 2012). The second approach, mostly carried out by international NGOs like the Gate Foundation, United Nations Food Programme, the UN Refugee Agency, and the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) centers on building resilient communities through Countering Violent Extremism (CVE) and most recently through PVE; providing humanitarian relief to Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs); disarmament, de-radicalization, and reintegration of ex-combatants. The government, in a long-term peacebuilding strategy also created the Northeast Development Commission (NEDC) for reconciliation and reconstruction in the region (Managing Conflict in Nigeria, 2020). One of the most discussed peacebuilding strategies by the Nigeria State is the Operation Safe Corridor (OPSC) that was lunched by the Federal government in 2015 to serve as a “safe exit” pathway for repentant Boko Haram fighters (Owonikoko, 2022). Though this programme has been condemned by many observers as an insult to the plight of victims of the barbaric activities of Boko Haram, it is however, painfully, a peacebuilding strategy that have gained acceptance all over the world.

Despite the positive impact of these peacebuilding interventions,

there seems to be no lasting solution to insecurity in the country and particularly the Northeast region. Though Boko Haram has been decimated to an extent, the humanitarian crises occasioned by the insurgency and other violent conflicts are still ravaging the region. This is because the entire peacebuilding architecture in the region has been marred by various problems that seems unsurmountable. The objective of this paper therefore is to explore the problems associated with peacebuilding in the Northeast region of Nigeria, from the prism of NGOs and to make practicable recommendations on the way forward.

Literature Review

NGOs and Peacebuilding in Africa

The important role NGOs play in peacebuilding endeavours all over Africa cannot be overemphasized. Since decolonization, African states have been grappling with violent intra-state conflicts, some of which have become intractable (Amaechi, 2017). International and community-based NGOs have been intervening at various stages, either during or after conflicts. As a result, they have become an integral part of the players in the fields of peace, security, reconciliation, and general development since the post-cold war era (Piquard, 2022). Africa is no doubt a budding ground for international and local NGOs engaging in various activities aimed at building peace in the troubled continent. These activities cut across humanitarian services, conflict resolution, reconciliation, mediation, capacity building, economic aids, education, infrastructural development, health services, human rights, accountability and transparency, environmental peace, and promotion of social justice (Chris et al., 2021). The underlying aim is to deal with the root causes of conflict and build sustainable peace and development. Saaida (2023) recognizes the importance of community ownership and involvement through NGOs in the quest to building peace in any society. This section explored what NGOs have done and

are still doing in respect to peacebuilding in Africa. The challenges, successes, and prospects are also highlighted.

In the area of capacity building on conflict early warning systems, the West Africa Network for Peacebuilding (WANEP) has been at the forefront in developing and operationalizing an early warning system in conjunction with the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and the broader African Peace and Security Architecture (APSA) of the African Union (AU) (Eze & Frimpong, 2021). This system is known as the ECOWAS Early Warning and Response Network (ECOWARN) which operates at national, regional, and continental levels. ECOWARN has been able to guide policy makers on emerging security threats in the sub-region and the appropriate response. At the national level, ECOWARN has also developed National Early Warning Systems (NEWS) in all ECOWAS member states in order to ensure more community ownership and participation in the over-all peacebuilding architecture (Adegboye et al., 2023). The protracted conflict in Northern Uganda also attracted various interventions by NGOs, especially in the area of human rights violations that majorly characterize the conflict. On human rights advocacy in Northern Uganda, Human Rights Focus (HURIFO), a human rights NGO released a report in 2002 called “Between Two Fires” that highlighted the gruesome violations of human rights by both the Lord Resistance Army (LRA) and the Ugandan armed forces. This advocacy led to the reduction in violence and spread of democratic principles in theory and practice (Opongo, 2011).

In Africa, there is no country that depicts the importance and involvement of NGOs in peacebuilding like Liberia. The 14 years wars in the country saw the proliferation of international and local NGOs that led to the common cliché among locals that says “When the war came, development came” (Fuest, 2010, p. 10). The author further states that, by February 2007, over 400 local NGOs were legally established in the country with the Ministry of Planning and Economic Affairs. This was made possible with external funding

from over 180 international NGOs operating in the country by the year 2008. Majorly, these local NGOs were engaged in fighting acute poverty, reconciliation, constitutional reforms, and general humanitarian services.

Notwithstanding their important role, NGOs in Africa are constantly grappling with various challenges that affects the effectiveness and impact of their peacebuilding activities. One of the major challenges is dependence of local NGOs on external funding (Lenshie et al., 2024). This dependence on external funding influences their agenda and can question their autonomy, credibility, as well as the sustainability and effectiveness of their peacebuilding initiatives. NGOs working on peacebuilding initiatives amidst an ongoing violence are routinely faced with security risks that hinders their penetration into vulnerable communities that are trapped and needs more humanitarian assistance (Paffenholz, 2021). NGOs have also been accused of fueling conflicts in cases where there is lack of conflict sensitive development (Paudel et al., 2023). In trying to build peace, they end up exacerbating or even creating a new conflict. This is mostly as a result of top-bottom approach where the interveners have no good knowledge of the context, they are working on by neglecting the bottom-top approach that ensures community participation and ownership (Akande et al., 2021).

The prospect of NGOs and peacebuilding in Africa can be strengthened to be more effective when there is high practice of collaboration, coordination, and knowledge sharing between and among different actors working in the continent. This involves a clear and honest partnership between government agencies, international and local NGOs, and people at the grassroots (Bojicic-Dzelilovic & Martin, 2020). Furthermore, the recognition and inclusion of gender sensitive initiatives have become very necessary (Hillenbrand et al., 2023). Women, children, and other marginalized groups have been said to be the most vulnerable in terms of violence. It is therefore more appropriate to approach

interventions from their own perspectives. This will ensure more effectiveness and impact.

A Review of Some Peacebuilding Activities in Northeastern Nigeria

This section highlights some peacebuilding activities carried out by state and non-state actors in the Northeast. On the short term, peacebuilding activities in the Northeast have been on humanitarian assistance to IDPs and communities affected by the insurgency. The National Emergency Agency (NEMA) and the State Emergency Agencies (SEMAs) have been coordinating the distribution of relief materials to IDPs and host communities. Huge amount of money has gone into provision of food, shelter, security, clean water, and other emergency needs for IDPs in various camps in Maiduguri, Yobe, Adamawa, and neighboring states of Bauchi, Gombe and Taraba. There are hundreds of IDP camps in the region that are under the control of NEMA and SEMAs.

One of the major peacebuilding activities in the Northeast is the Safe School Initiative (SSI) by the federal Government where schools are provided with security personnel and students are transferred to low risk states within the region to ensure continuation of learning (UNDP, 2017). International NGOs like the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) and the Red Crescent have all been engaging in humanitarian services across the Northeast. According to a report (Borno Strategic Resilience Assessment) by Mercy Corps (2018), over \$2 billion have been expended recently on humanitarian assistance in the Northeast. Kerschbaum (2019) argues that though international humanitarian response in the Northeast was late, they were able to deliver substantially within a short period of time. He cited an example with the United State Agency for International Development (USAID) where \$291 million dollars was spent in 2017 alone as against "...virtually nothing in 2014..." (p. 6). On the long term, international humanitarian assistance has also involved collaborative efforts on military hardware and funds toward rebuilding the Northeast (Ada

& Abdullahi, 2022). Figure 2 shows a graphical representation of international humanitarian assistance (both appealed and funded) from 2014-2017.

Fig. 2: Levels of international humanitarian assistance in millions of US dollars (appealed and funded) 2014-2017. Source: OCHA Financial Tracking System (FTS), adopted by Famine Response and Prevention in Northeast Nigeria

From Figure 2, it is clear that funded international humanitarian assistance rose from merely below \$200 million in 2014 to over \$800 million in 2017. This can be attributed to the fact that the insurgency would have been suppressed earlier if these responses came earlier too. It also shows that these international humanitarian actors are more focused on post-conflict peacebuilding than ongoing peacebuilding efforts.

Apart from the broad humanitarian, economic recovery, post-conflict reconstruction peacebuilding activities, there are other various ways in which peacebuilding have been carried out in the Northeast by the federal and state governments, national and international NGOs and particularly, community based organizations (CBOs). These include but not limited to: media support, dialogue, traditional justice and reconciliation, conflict sensitive development, inclusion, security, civic education, heritage and cultural preservation (Mali & Rinkat, 2021). CVE and PVE have also been very important components of the entire peacebuilding architecture in the Northeast. This involves the

use of religious leaders to teach and propagate right dictates of religion, particularly Islam. Another aspect of peacebuilding in the Northeast that has generated and still generating a lot of debates is the OPSC of the Federal Government of Nigeria. The aim of the programme is to disarm, deradicalize, rehabilitate, and reintegrate repentant Boko Haram members into their various communities. This post-conflict peacebuilding activity started in September 2015 and as at December 2022, 900 ex-combatants have graduated from the scheme (Hassana, 2022). Despite the good intention of the programme, it has, however, received a lot of criticisms, especially from victims of the insurgency. The argument has been that, it is unfair and an injustice to compensate criminals with “a good life” while the victims of their atrocities are still living with the scars of war with little or no attention from the government (Ugwueze & Onuoha, 2022).

Multitrack Diplomacy: A Model of Analysis

This study adopts multitrack diplomacy (MTD) as a model to explain the phenomenon of peacebuilding in the context of the Northeast. MTD was developed by Ambassador John W. McDonald and Dr. Louise Diamond of the Institute for Multi-Track Diplomacy (IMTD) in 1991 in their book *Multi-Track Diplomacy, a systems approach to peace* (McDonald, 2012). MTD is a multi-dimensional strategy for peace that involves all stakeholders in any given conflict context. The thesis of MTD is that peace in a society has different constituencies. Focusing on one or blaming the government particularly is simplistic. It advocates for a holistic strategy that requires the involvement of every aspect of a society in order to achieve sustainable peace and development. It is a system-based approach to peacebuilding with nine tracks that are captured in the figure 3:

Fig. 3: Nine tracks of multitrack diplomacy. Source: www.imtd.org

Figure 3 shows the nine tracks of MTD and how they are all connected. In relation to this study, peacebuilding is like building a house. Everybody must play its part from the foundation of the building to laying of bricks, roofing, and final interior work for it to be habitable. The foundation must be strong enough for the house to stand the test of time and pressure from storms. To build the peace edifice and surmount the problems associated with it in the Northeast therefore, all stakeholders from the nine tracks must work individually and collectively in order to achieve sustainable peace and development. The foundation of this peace edifice must be strong enough to hold the bricks and the roof. In this context, the foundation represents engaging in massive and efficient peace education advocacy in the country starting from the grassroots. This task can be taken by the academia in the nine tracks of Multi-Track Diplomacy. The culture of peace needs to be inculcated into pupils at a very early stage. The media can also do this by engaging

in a “catch them young” peace education television programme. From there, other structural issues in the society can be tackled systematically, building upon the established strong foundation.

The failure of security and the emergence and spread of insurgency in the Northeast can be attributed to the failure of the general society in the context of the nine tracks above. The peace edifice in the Northeast and Nigeria in general is collapsing because various segments of the society have failed in performing their functions effectively. The theory of structural functionalism is very much obtainable here. The government; NGOs; the business community; private citizens; research, training, and education; peace activists; religious leaders and institutions; funding actors; and communication and the media have all failed to an extent.

Methods

This study adopted mixed methods research design for data collection and analysis. Qualitative data were collected through key informant interviews (KII). To this effect, 20 NGOs staff who are currently in the field working on various aspects of peacebuilding in Borno and Adamawa States were interviewed. Interview question was open ended which allowed the respondents the liberty of expressing themselves to the fullest. Because the study has only one research objective (to explore the problems of peacebuilding in The Northeast), the interview question was also one, with follow up questions that were based on the answers of the respondents. Interviews were transcribed and fitted into the research objective in the discussion section of the paper.

Quantitative data were collected through a structured questionnaire, titled Problems of Peacebuilding in the Northeast Questionnaire (PPNNQ). The questionnaire, containing ten items based on Likert scale, was shared among different sample population working on peacebuilding in Borno and Adamawa states. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A collected demographic information of respondents, namely sex,

age, marital status, and level of education. Section B had ten items on broad based and local/community problems of peacebuilding in The Northeast. Items 1-5 represent broad based problems while items 6-10 represent local or community-based problems of peacebuilding in The Northeast. The questionnaire was distributed among a purposive sample population including 160 NGOs staff, 20 NEMA officials, and 20 security agents all shared equally between Borno and Adamawa states. This makes a total of 200 questionnaire. 162 filled questionnaires were retrieved out of 200. 12 were invalid while 150 were valid and constitute the analyzed data for this study. Data were analyzed using simple descriptive statistical tools which include figures, tables, percentages, and charts. Both qualitative and quantitative data were triangulated in order to complement each other in terms of weaknesses.

Results

This section presents the findings of the research, starting with the demographic information of the respondents which include sex, age, and educational status.

Fig. 4: Sex distribution of respondents. Source: Authors' fieldwork, 2023

From Figure 4, it can be seen that 85 respondents representing 57% are male, while 65 respondents representing 43% are female.

This difference is not unconnected with the risk associated with working in conflict locations in the Northeast region of Nigeria, which the former are more likely to take than the latter.

Fig. 5: Age distribution of respondents. Source: Authors' fieldwork, 2023

As seen in Figure 5, it is not out of place to infer that the respondents are old enough to understand the phenomenon under investigation and can make informed choices on the items in the PPNNQ questionnaire.

Fig. 6: Educational status of respondents. Source: Authors' fieldwork, 2023

Figure 6 shows that almost all of the respondents are well educated, implying that their view was based on a comprehension of the

phenomenon. It also implies that their responses can be trusted given their degree of literacy, experience, and grasp of the subject matter.

Table 2: Frequency distribution of responses on the broad and community based problems of peacebuilding in the Northeast

Item	SA	A	D	SD
Lack of government cooperation and commitment	90	45	15	0
Continued insecurity and displacement	105	30	15	0
Inadequate regional cooperation	84	66	0	0
Ungoverned spaces	90	60	0	0
Lack of adequate funding	60	45	30	0
Militarization of return areas	15	60	60	15
The reluctance of displaced persons to return to their communities	90	45	15	0
Family separation	60	60	30	0
Housing, land, and property problems	90	45	15	0
Lack of basic services	45	30	0	75

Source: Authors' fieldwork, 2023

Fig. 7: Percentage distribution of responses on the broad and community based problems of peacebuilding in northeast Nigeria. Source: Authors' fieldwork, 2023

Discussion of Findings

This study explored the problems of peacebuilding in the Northeast region of Nigeria from the prism of NGOs. The results revealed that there are broad based and local/community-based problems of peacebuilding in this region. The former includes lack of government cooperation and commitment, continued insecurity and displacement, inadequate regional cooperation, ungoverned spaces, and lack of adequate funding. The latter include militarization of return areas, reluctance of displaced persons to return to their communities, family separation, housing, land, and property problems, lack of basic services (shelter, health, and education).

Lack of government cooperation and commitment has been a major impediment to an effective peacebuilding engagement in the Northeast. From the results above, and from interviews, many respondents alluded to the fact that the Nigerian government and its agents have shown great lack of cooperation and commitment to rebuilding the Northeast from the shackles of Boko Haram insurgency. This is in line with the study of Kerschbaum (2019). To some respondents, this is not unconnected to corruption, nepotism, and use of public offices for self-aggrandizement. The view of an NGO staff in a KII is worth noting:

Since we started our humanitarian engagements in Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe States in 2012, the Nigeria government and its officials have shown great lack of cooperation and commitment to dealing with the humanitarian crisis in the region. We have experiences where government will frustrate your efforts if they are not in charge of implementing your projects. Even when they are allowed to implement these projects, they end up becoming ineffective or even incomplete. The worst part is seeing officials diverting relief materials for personal use. I believe you have seen relief materials meant for IDPs in open markets for sale.

Continued insecurity and displacement in the Northeast have been highlighted by virtually all respondents as a major problem to peacebuilding. NGOs staff, NEMA officials, and some security agents all attested to the fact that the failure of the government to end all forms of active attacks is impeding the successful implementation of their peacebuilding programmes, especially in ungoverned spaces. This is also another major problem affecting peacebuilders in the region. There is vast land, water ways, and forested areas in the region that have little or no presence of the government nor its security agents. These are villages with people who are constantly being affected by the insurgency, and recently, by banditry. But they have received little or no attention from the state and other international and local NGOs. Though NGOs workers have blamed their helplessness in reaching these ungoverned spaces on safety concerns.

Inadequate regional cooperation and funding have also been identified by majority of respondents as some of the major obstacles to peacebuilding in the Northeast region of Nigeria. For the former, as Uche and Akpuru-Aja (2018) rightly pointed out, there has always been a challenge from states like Cameroon, Chad and Niger in the counterterrorism struggles by the MJTF, as retrieving terrorists often finds refuge at the borders of these countries. The situation has escalated, especially with Niger because of the recent coup-d'état that has created a political crisis between the country and ECOWAS under the leadership of Nigeria. Funding is, no doubt, a leveler in any human endeavour. The problem of funding is broad based and also local. In fact, KII respondents identified lack of funding as the single most important part of their activities. Kelechi et al. (2021) affirmed this in their study when they assert that lack of adequate funding has been a major challenge to peacebuilding in the Northeast. A founder and executive director of a CBO in Adamawa state recounts his challenge with lack of funding thus:

We have a lot of problems facing us in this industry.

However, the first and major issue is lack of adequate funding. As a local and non-profit organization, we are close to the people. We see their sufferings every day. But we can only do little because it is very hard to get funding from international and local donors. Because of corruption and other illegalities in the country, the process of getting grants and other donations have become very tedious that sometimes you feel like quitting.

The quoted view above is in tandem with the study of Lenshie et al. (2024) in which they discovered that external resource dependence affects, to a very large extent, the activities of CBOs in Northeast, Nigeria. They assert that CBOs in Nigeria rely heavily on external donor agencies, NGOs, and other organizations for finance, logistics, materials, and even training, which in turn influences their types of programmes, training content and accountability.

On local/community-based problems, transcribed KII data, triangulated with the quantitative results presented above, revealed that most of the identified problems include militarization of return areas, reluctance of displaced persons to return to their communities, family separation, housing, land, and property problems, lack of basic services (shelter, health, and education). However, a striking and unexpected finding in this study is that, 50% of respondents strongly disagreed with the assertion that lack of basic services (shelter, health, and education) are some of the major problems associated with peacebuilding in The Northeast. Even though the remaining 50% generally accepted the assertion, it is still an unexpected point of departure from extant literature like Kerschbaum (2019); Kelechi et al. (2021); Hassana (2022); Ugwueze et al., (2022); and Lenshie et al. (2023).

Conclusion

This study has been able to establish the fact that there are many problems facing NGOs working on peacebuilding in the Northeast region of Nigeria. The result is clear and sufficient enough to make generalization on the problems of peacebuilding in Nigeria. The study provides a concise exposition into the broad-based and community-based problems of peacebuilding. These include lack of government cooperation and commitment, continued insecurity and displacement, inadequate regional cooperation, ungoverned spaces, and lack of adequate funding, militarization of return areas, reluctance of displaced persons to return to their communities, family separation, housing, land, and property problems, lack of basic services (shelter, health, and education). To this end, based on the MTD model of analysis for this study, all stakeholders in the country and outside the country should join hands together to surmount these problems and build the peace edifice in Nigeria. Peacebuilding is not an exclusive reserve for the government nor the NGOs, but for everybody in the society. Therefore, all individuals and organizations representing the nine tracks of MTD should engage more in peacebuilding, especially in the aspect of funding, tackling current insecurity, increasing government cooperation and commitment, ensuring government and security agents reaches more ungoverned spaces, and increase ownership to housing, land and property giving people a sense of belonging to the Nigeria project.

R E F E R E N C E S

- Abeeb, A. M. (2020). Peace building and conflict prevention as means toward curtailing violent conflicts in North-Eastern, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Applied Management and Social Sciences*, 20, 111-122
- Achebe, C. (2013). There was a country: A personal history of Biafra. *Choice Reviews Online*, 51(2), 51–1026. <https://doi.org/10.5860/choice.51-1026>

- Ada, J. E., & Abdullahi, M. (2022). The impact of humanitarian aid on post conflict development in Borno State. *International Journal of Peace and Development Studies*, 13(1), 1-16.
- Adegboye, L. A., Zamani, A. P., Meyeyin-Bala, K., Amakiri, H. O., Haruna, M. L., & Adama, M. A. (2023). Assessing ECOWAS early warning response networks and stand by force in resolving challenges in West Africa. *International Journal of Social Science, Management, Peace and Conflict Research*, 1(8), 163-177.
- Akande, O., Kaye, S., & Rukuni, T. (2021). The efficacy of community peacebuilding in African communities: Case studies from Nigeria and Zimbabwe. *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development*, 16(3), 303-317. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15423166211034567>
- Akoji, S. J., & Abaji, A. S. (2025). The 2022 multidimensional poverty index of Nigeria: A sociological review. *Pan-African Journal of Governance and Development*, 6(1), 141-168.
- Amaechi, C. M. (2017). Africa's 'intractable' conflicts and the imperative of the indigenous idea of peacebuilding. *Conflict Studies Quarterly*, 20, 1-15.
- Ashindorbe, K., Afatakpa, F., & Owonikoko, S. B. (2021). Civilian Joint Task Force and Nigeria's counter-terrorism operation: A critique of the community-based approach to insecurity. *African Security*, 14(3), 286-305. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19392206.2021.1998977>
- Bojicic-Dzelilovic, V., & Martin, M. (2020). Wholly local? Ownership as philosophy and practice in peacebuilding interventions. In V. Bojicic-Dzelilovic & M. Martin (Eds.), *Whole-of-Society Peacebuilding* (pp. 47-61). Routledge.
- Chris, O. I., Victor, O., & Felicia, C. (2021). Non-governmental organizations (NGOs), conflict and peace building in Africa. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Education and Research*, 6(2), 32-42.
- Eze, C. B., & Frimpong, O. B. (2020). Contributions of early warning to the African peace and security architecture: The experience of the West Africa Network for Peacebuilding (WANEP). In *The state of peacebuilding in Africa: Lessons learned for policymakers and practitioners* (pp. 181-194). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Fuest, V. (2010). Contested inclusions: Pitfalls of NGO peace-building activities in Liberia. *Africa Spectrum*, 45(2), 3-33.

- Hassana, I. (2022). Reintegrating ex-combatants: An assessment of operation safe corridor Journal for Deradicalization, 33, 150-180.
- Hillenbrand, E., Mohanraj, P., Njuki, J., Ntakobakinvuna, D., & Sitotaw, A. T. (2023). “There is still something missing”: comparing a gender-sensitive and gender-transformative approach in Burundi. *Development in Practice*, 33(4), 451-462.
- Kelechi, N. O., Maiangwa, J. S., & Ularju, V. (2021). Interrogating the state and challenges of peacebuilding in Borno State, Nigeria. *Jalingo Journal of Peace Science and Conflict Management*, 1(1), 43-52.
- Kerschbaum, A. (2019). Stabilizing northeast Nigeria after Boko Haram. *Zeitschrift Für Strategische Analysen*, 3(4), 413-414. <https://doi.org/10.1515/sirius-2019-4007>
- Lenshie, N. E., Miapyen, B. S., Ganiyu, A. D., Maiangwa, J. S., & Ezeibe, C. (2024). Does dependence on external resources affect community-based organizations’ efforts in countering violent extremism? An explorative study of the northeast Nigeria experience. *Democracy and Security*, 20(2), 153-178.
- Mali, H. & Rinkat, O. (2021). Peace building strategies used by non-governmental organization in mitigating the effect of Boko Haram crises in northeast. *Nigeria International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research*, 3(3), 84-94
- McDonald, J. W. (2012). The Institute for Multi-Track Diplomacy. *Journal of Conflictology*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.7238/joc.v3i2.1629>
- Mercy Corps (2018). Borno, northeast Nigeria strategic resilience assessment full report and findings. Retrieved September 13, 2023, from https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2019-11/prg_bornostrategicresiliencessassmenet_r_lo_0319_web_v3.pdf.
- Nnam, M. U., Ugwuoke, C. O., Njemanze, V. C., & Akwara, F. A. (2020). Boko Haram terrorism and human security in Nigeria: Matters arising. *Journal of Aggression, Maltreatment & Trauma*, 29(10), 1257-1278.
- Opongo, E. O. (2012). NGO peacebuilding in northern Uganda: interrogating liberal peace from the ground (Doctoral Thesis). University of Bradford.
- Owonikoko, S. B. (2022). “Take them to Government House or Aso Rock”: Community receptivity to reintegration of Operation Safe Corridor’s deradicalized ex-Boko Haram members in Northeastern Nigeria. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2021.2015884>

- Paffenholz, T. (2021). Perpetual peacebuilding: a new paradigm to move beyond the linearity of liberal peacebuilding. *Journal of Intervention and Statebuilding*, 15(3), 367-385.
- Paudel, P., Subedi, D. B., & Winterford, K. (2023). A conflict-sensitivity dilemma: how conflict denialism constrains spaces for conflict-sensitive actions for peacebuilding. *Development in Practice*, 33(5), 599–611. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614524.2023.2220990>
- Piquard, B. (2022). What knowledge counts? Local humanitarian knowledge production in protracted conflicts. A Central African Republic case study. *Peacebuilding*, 10(1), 85-100.
- Saaida, M. (2023). Local ownership and community-based approaches to peace building. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 10(10), 66-71.
- Uche, C., & Akpuru-Aja, A. (2018). An assessment of peacebuilding policy implementation strategy in the The Northeast. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 5(6), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.14445/23942703/ijhss-v5i6p101>
- Ugwueze, M. I., Ngwu, E. C., & Onuoha, F. C. (2021). Operation Safe Corridor programme and reintegration of ex-Boko Haram fighters in Nigeria. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 57(6), 1229–1248. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00219096211047996>.